

	Demographic Data									Q = QUESTION
	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q5	Q6	Q7	Q8	Q9	P = PARTICIPANT
P1	Master's degree	Man	Dev	CLT	Remote	More than 5	up to 5	SP	No	
P2	Specialist	Man	Dev	CLT	Remote	between 1 and 2	more than 50	MG	No	
P3	Specialist	Man	Diretor	CLT	In person	More than 5	21 to 50	SC	Abragames	
P4	Specialist	Man	CEO	independent	Remote	More than 5	up to 5	PR	No	
P5	Specialist	Woman	CEO	Partner	Hybrid	between 1 and 2	11 to 20	RS	Adjogos and Abragames	
P6	Graduate	Man	CEO, Game Designer, Dev	independent	Remote	Up to 1 year	up to 5	SP	No	
P7	Specialist	Man	Diretor	CLT	Hybrid	More than 5	21 to 50	SP	Abragames	
P8	Specialist	Woman	CEO	Profit distribution	Remote	More than 5	21 to 50	SC	Abragames and ASCjogos	
P9	High School	Man	Game Designer, Partner (small business)	independent	Remote	More than 5	6 to 10	PR	No	
P10	Graduate	Man	CEO, Diretor, PO, UX Designer, Game Designer, Administrative, Test Analyst	Partner	Remote	between 3 and 4	6 to 10	PE	No	
P11	Graduate	Man	Director, CCO	independent	Remote	between 1 and 2	up to 5	SP	Abragames	
P12	Specialist	Woman	Director, Game Designer, Dev, Administrative Test Analyst	Indie	Remote	between 3 and 4	up to 5	MG	No	
P13	High School	Man	CEO	Owner	In person	between 3 and 4	up to 5	SP	ABRAGAMES, HUB DE GAMES SJC	
P14	Specialist	Man	CEO, Game Designer, Dev	independent	Remote	More than 5	up to 5	MG	No	
P15	Specialist	Man	CEO, Director, UX Designer, Game Designer, Dev, UI Designer, Administrative, Test Analyst, The "company" is made up of me, and that's it! So I kind of occupy all those marked areas.	CLT	Remote	between 1 and 2	up to 5	PB	No	
P16	Specialist	Man	CEO	independent	In person	between 3 and 4	up to 5	PR	No	
P17	Graduate	Man	Dev	independent	Hybrid	between 1 and 2	21 to 50	SP	N/A	
P18	Graduate	Man	CEO	Businessperson/Owner	Remote	More than 5	11 to 20	SC	ASCJogos, Abragames	
P19	Graduate	Man	Dev	independent	Remote	between 1 and 2	up to 5	SP	No	
P20	Graduate	Man	CEO, UX Designer, Game Designer	independent	Remote	More than 5	up to 5	SP	No	
P21	Specialist	Woman	CEO	Businessperson	Remote	between 3 and 4	up to 5	RS	AdjogosRS	
P22	Graduate	Man	CEO, Director, PO, UX Designer, Game Designer, Dev, UI Designer, Administrative	Businessperson	Remote	More than 5	6 to 10	SP	SP Jogos; Abragames	
P23	Graduate	Man	Game Designer	independent	Remote	between 3 and 4	21 to 50	RJ	No	
P24	Graduate	Man	Director, PO, UX Designer, Game Designer, Administrative	Partner	Remote	More than 5	up to 5	RJ	RING	
P25	Graduate	Man	CEO, Game Designer, Art	independent	Remote	between 1 and 2	up to 5	SP	No	
P26	Specialist	Woman	CEO	Partner	Remote	More than 5	up to 5	PR	No	
P27	Specialist	Man	CEO	independent	Hybrid	between 1 and 2	6 to 10	RJ	RING	
P28	Graduate	Woman	All	independent	Hybrid	More than 5	up to 5	RS	No	
P29	Specialist	Man	CEO, UX Designer, Game Designer, Dev, UI Designer	independent	In person	between 3 and 4	up to 5	SP	No	

P30	Graduate	Man	CEO, Diretor, PO, UX Designer, Game Designer, Desenvolvedor, UI Designer, Administrativo, Analista de Testes	independent	In person	between 1 and 2	up to 5	MA	Amagames
P31	Specialist	Man	Director, Game Designer, Dev, UI Designer, Administrative	Owner	In person	More than 5	up to 5	RS	No
P32	Graduate	refer not to ans	CEO, Director, PO, UX Designer, Game Designer, Dev, UI Designer, Administrative, Test Analyst	independent	In person	More than 5	up to 5	RN	No
P33	Graduate	Man	CEO, Game Designer, Dev, Administrative	independent	Remote	Up to 1 year	up to 5	RJ	RING and Atragames
P34	Graduate	Man	CEO, Dev	Partner	Remote	More than 5	11 to 20	DF	Atragames and Abring
P35	Graduate	Man	CEO, UX Designer, Game Designer, Dev, Administrative	Partner	Remote	between 3 and 4	up to 5	MA	AMAGAMES
P36	Specialist	Man	Director, Game Designer	independent	In person	More than 5	up to 5	RJ	No
P37	PhD	Non-Binary	Game Designer, Producer	Partner	Remote	More than 5	up to 5	PR	No
P38	Master's degree	Man	CEO, Game Designer, Dev	independent	Remote	More than 5	up to 5	SP	No
P39	Master's degree	Woman	CEO, Director, UX Designer, Game Designer, Creative Director, Game Producer, Narrative Designer	independent	Hybrid	More than 5	up to 5	RJ	RING, Gaming
P40	Graduate	Man	CEO, Director, PO, UX Designer, Game Designer, Dev, UI Designer, Administrative, Test Analyst, Solodev	independent	In person	between 3 and 4	up to 5	MG	No
P41	High School	Man	CEO	Partner	Remote	between 1 and 2	6 to 10	RJ	ACJOGOS-RJ, old RING.
P42	Graduate	Man	Game Designer, Dev	CLT	In person	between 1 and 2	6 to 10	SC	Atragames
P43	Graduate	Man	Director	Outsourced	Remote	Up to 1 year	6 to 10	SP	ABRAGAMES
P44	Graduate	Woman	Marketing	PJ	Remote	between 3 and 4	11 to 20	RS	Ad jogos
P45	Master's degree	Man	CEO, Director, UX Designer, Game Designer, UI Designer	independent	Remote	More than 5	up to 5	SP	No
P46	Graduate	Man	CEO, Director, UX Designer, Game Designer, Dev, UI Designer, Administrative, Test Analyst	independent	Remote	between 1 and 2	up to 5	MG	No
P47	Master's degree	Man	UX Designer	CLT	In person	More than 5	more than 50	RS	No
P48	High School	Man	CEO, Director, PO, UX Designer, Game Designer, Dev, UI Designer, Administrative, Test Analyst	independent	In person	between 1 and 2	up to 5	MG	No
P49	Specialist	Man	Game Designer	CLT	Remote	Up to 1 year	more than 50	PE	N/A
P50	Graduate	Man	Game Designer, Dev	PJ	Hybrid	Up to 1 year	21 to 50	CE	Ascende Jogos
P51	Specialist	Man	Game Designer, UI Designer	Outsourced	Remote	between 3 and 4	up to 5	RS	No
P52	Graduate	Man	UX Designer, UI Designer	CLT	Remote	between 3 and 4	more than 50	MG	No
P53	Master's degree	Man	UX Designer, UI Designer	independent	Remote	between 1 and 2	21 to 50	SP	Main Leaf
P54	High School	Man	UX Designer, Game Designer, Dev, UI Designer	independent	Remote	Up to 1 year	up to 5	MG	No
P55	Graduate	Man	Administrative	CLT	In person	between 3 and 4	more than 50	SP	No
P56	High School	Woman	UI Designer	independent	Remote	Up to 1 year	21 to 50	MG	No

P57	Graduate	Man	Producer	Outsourced	In person	Up to 1 year	more than 50	SP	Abragames
P58	Graduate	Man	Game Designer	independent	Remote	between 3 and 4	6 to 10	SP	No
P59	Graduate	Man	Dev	independent	Remote	More than 5	up to 5	MG	No
P60	Graduate	Man	Dev	independent	Remote	between 3 and 4	11 to 20	PA	N/a
P61	Specialist	Man	Game Designer	CLT	In person	between 3 and 4	11 to 20	SP	No
P62	High School	Man	Dev	independent	Remote	between 1 and 2	6 to 10	RS	ADJogosRS
P63	High School	Man	Game Designer, UI Designer, Artist 2d/3d	independent	Remote	between 3 and 4	up to 5	SP	No
P64	Graduate	Man	CEO, Administrative, Tech art and 3D Modeler	independent	Hybrid	More than 5	up to 5	RS	ADJogosRS
P65	Graduate	Woman	Game producer	Estagiária	Remote	between 1 and 2	more than 50	SP	No
P66	Specialist	refer not to ans	Agile Coach	CLT	Hybrid	More than 5	more than 50	RJ	N/A
P67	Graduate	Woman	Narrative Designer	Outsourced	Remote	between 3 and 4	more than 50	RS	Abragames
P68	Master's degree	Man	Dev	Outsourced	Remote	More than 5	more than 50	SP	Abragames
P69	Graduate	Man	Dev	CLT	Remote	between 1 and 2	more than 50	SP	No
P70	Graduate	Woman	UX Designer, Game Designer, Dev, UI Designer	independent	Remote	Up to 1 year	up to 5	SP	No
P71	Specialist	Man	CEO	independent	Remote	More than 5	11 to 20	SP	Abragames
P72	Specialist	Woman	Game Designer, Level Designer	independent	Remote	between 1 and 2	11 to 20	RS	Not respond
P73	Graduate	Non-Binary	Game Designer	Outsourced	Remote	Up to 1 year	6 to 10	RJ	N/A
P74	Graduate	Man	Director, UI Designer	independent	Remote	between 3 and 4	up to 5	PE	Abragames
P75	Graduate	Man	Game Designer	PJ	Remote	Up to 1 year	21 to 50	MS	No
P76	High School	refer not to ans	freelancer artist and design	independent	Remote	Up to 1 year	up to 5	SP	No
P77	PhD	Man	UX Designer, UI Designer, Lead UI/UX / Professor/Coordinator	CLT	In person	More than 5	more than 50	PB	No
P78	Graduate	Man	Product Owner - Game Designer - Dev	independent	Remote	Up to 1 year	6 to 10	SP	No
P79	Graduate	Woman	Test Analyst	CLT	In person	Up to 1 year	more than 50	SP	Tiny Build
P80	High School	Man	Game Designer	PJ	Remote	between 1 and 2	more than 50	RS	ADJogos RS
P81	Specialist	Man	Director, UX Designer, Game Designer, Dev, UI Designer, Administrative	independent	Remote	More than 5	up to 5	SC	Abragames and ASCJogos
P82	PhD	Man	Director	CLT + Advisor PJ	Hybrid	More than 5	more than 50	SP	Abragames
P83	Graduate	Woman	Administrative	independent	Remote	between 1 and 2	more than 50	RJ	Dumativa
P84	Graduate	Woman	PO	independent	Remote	between 1 and 2	11 to 20	SP	Abragames
P85	High School	Non-Binary	UX Designer, UI Designer	independent	Remote	between 1 and 2	21 to 50	RS	No
P86	High School	Man	CEO	Partner	Hybrid	between 3 and 4	6 to 10	PE	Playnanbuco and Abragames
P87	Graduate	Man	CEO, Director, Dev, Test Analyst	Outsourced	Remote	between 3 and 4	6 to 10	SP	Abragames
P88	Graduate	Woman	QA Lead	independent	Remote	between 1 and 2	21 to 50	SP	NO
P89	Graduate	Woman	Director, PO, Producer	independent	Remote	between 1 and 2	11 to 20	AM	No
P90	Graduate	Woman	Dev	independent	Remote	Up to 1 year	up to 5	RJ	No
P91	Graduate	Man	Dev, 3D Artist	independent	Remote	Up to 1 year	up to 5	RJ	No
P92	Master's degree	Man	Dev	CLT	Remote	between 3 and 4	11 to 20	AM	No
P93	Graduate	Woman	CEO, Animator e Art Director	independent	Remote	between 1 and 2	6 to 10	DF	No
P94	Specialist	Woman	Game Designer	independent	Remote	Up to 1 year	more than 50	RS	N/A

P95	Graduate	Man	Production Assist	independent	Remote	between 1 and 2	up to 5	SP	No
P96	Graduate	Man	Game Designer	independent	Remote	between 1 and 2	6 to 10	PI	No
P97	Graduate	Man	Dev	CLT	Remote	between 1 and 2	more than 50	PE	OV entertainment
P98	Graduate	Man	CEO, Director	independent	In person	between 3 and 4	6 to 10	SP	Mentorias Games Brazil
P99	Specialist	Man	CEO, Director, UX Designer, Game Designer, Dev, UI Designer, Administrative, Marketing, Social Media	independent	In person	between 1 and 2	up to 5	SC	My company is not yet part of any association, but I am looking to join ASCJogos for the time being.
P100	Graduate	Non-Binary	CEO, Game Designer	independent	Remote	between 1 and 2	up to 5	SC	No
P101	High School	Man	CEO, UX Designer, Game Designer, Dev, UI Designer	independent	Remote	Up to 1 year	up to 5	PR	PUCPR e Laje Studio
P102	Graduate	Man	UX Designer, Dev	independent	Remote	Up to 1 year	11 to 20	SP	No
P103	Graduate	Man	Game Designer	independent	Remote	between 1 and 2	up to 5	CE	Ascende
P104	Master's degree	Woman	CEO, Director, Game Designer	independent	Remote	More than 5	6 to 10	RJ	RING
P105	Specialist	Man	CEO, Dev	independent	Remote	between 1 and 2	up to 5	SP	No
P106	High School	Man	Game Designer	Student	Remote	More than 5	up to 5	SP	No
P107	High School	Man	Pharmacy clerk, but I also do pixel art animation work	independent	Remote	Up to 1 year	up to 5	SP	I worked on a few projects, one of the coolest was a cat game made using a guitar pedal.
P108	Graduate	prefer not to ans	Game Designer, Narrative Designer	independent	Remote	Up to 1 year	up to 5	SP	No
P109	Graduate	Man	UX Designer, UI Designer	CLT	Remote	between 3 and 4	more than 50	SP	No
P110	Graduate	Woman	Artist	independent	Remote	Up to 1 year	11 to 20	SP	No
P111	Graduate	Man	Game Designer, Dev	Scholarship	Hybrid	Up to 1 year	6 to 10	RJ	No
P112	Graduate	Woman	Game Designer	CLT	Remote	between 3 and 4	21 to 50	PE	N/A
P113	Master's degree	Man	CEO, Game Designer	independent	Remote	between 1 and 2	up to 5	MG	No
P114	PhD	Man	PO, UX Designer, Dev	Researcher	Hybrid	More than 5	more than 50	DF	No
P115	Graduate	Woman	Technical UI Artist	CLT	Remote	between 3 and 4	more than 50	SP	N/A
P116	Graduate	Man	Dev	independent	Remote	More than 5	up to 5	RJ	No
P117	High School	Man	compositor e sound designer	independent	Remote	Up to 1 year	up to 5	PR	No
P118	Graduate	Man	Dev	independent	Remote	Up to 1 year	up to 5	RS	No
P119	Graduate	Woman	Director	independent	Remote	between 1 and 2	21 to 50	RS	N/A
P120	Graduate	Man	Game Designer, Dev, UI Designer	y, but I have a game stud	Remote	Up to 1 year	up to 5	SC	No
P121	Graduate	Man	Dev	Outsourced	Remote	between 1 and 2	11 to 20	PR	No
P122	Master's degree	Man	I'm a teacher, I don't work for a company.	PROFESSOR	Hybrid	More than 5	more than 50	RS	No
P123	Graduate	Woman	Artist	Contract	Remote	Up to 1 year	up to 5	RS	No
P124	Graduate	Man	CEO	Partner	Remote	between 3 and 4	6 to 10	SP	No
P125	Graduate	Man	Game Designer, Dev	Outsourced	Remote	Up to 1 year	21 to 50	SP	No
P126	Graduate	Man	CEO, Game Designer	independent	In person	Up to 1 year	up to 5	SP	No
P127	Specialist	Woman	CEO/Game Designer/DEV	independent	Hybrid	More than 5	up to 5	SP	No
P128	Graduate	Man	DIRETOR/DEV	Partner	Remote	More than 5	up to 5	MA	AMAGAMES